

A COMPARISON BETWEEN SWARM INTELLIGENCE ALGORITHMS FOR ROUTING PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

Travelling salesman problem (TSP) is a most popular combinatorial routing problem, belongs to the class of NP-hard problems. Many approaches have been proposed for TSP. Among them, swarm intelligence (SI) algorithms can effectively achieve optimal tours with the minimum lengths and attempt to avoid trapping in local minima points. The transcendence of each SI is depended on the nature of the problem. In our studies, there has been yet no any article, which had compared the performance of SI algorithms for TSP perfectly. In this paper, four common SI algorithms are used to solve TSP, in order to compare the performance of SI algorithms for the TSP problem. These algorithms include genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimization, ant colony optimization, and artificial bee colony. For each SI, the various parameters and operators were tested, and the best values were selected for it. Experiments overcome benchmarks from TSPLIB show that artificial bee colony algorithm is the best one among the four SI-based methods to solve routing problems like TSP.

KEYWORDS

Travelling salesman problem (TSP), Swarm intelligence algorithms, Genetic algorithm (GA), Ant colony optimization (ACO), Particle swarm optimization (PSO), Artificial bee colony (ABC).

1. INTRODUCTION

Travelling salesman problem (TSP) is the most popular routing problem. It denotes a travelling salesman who wants to visit a number of nodes (cities) exactly once, and finally returns to the starting node (city). Objective of the problem is to determine a tour with the minimum distance. TSP is a sub-problem of many applications such as transportation [1], wireless communications [2], vehicle routing [3], integrated circuits [4] and semiconductor industries [5].

In recent years, many approaches have been developed for TSP, which can be classified into exact and approximate solutions [6]. Exact approaches, e.g., Branch & Bound [7], Branch & Cut [8], and Dynamic Programming [9], can only be performed for very small datasets. Therefore, researchers have to utilize approximate methods for the real-world problems. These approaches can find a set of near-optimal solutions in a reasonable time, rather than an exact algorithm that guarantees to achieve the optimal solution but in an exponential time. The operation of an exact method is to generate all possible tours, and select the best one with the minimum path length. The number of all possible permutations of N cities is $N!$, where each tour can be represented in $2N$ different manner according to the initial selected city and the direction of the tour. So the size of

the search space can be calculated according to Eq. (1). It is obviously that evaluation of all the $(N - 1)!/2$ solutions is practically impossible in term of computational time, even for 20 cities [10].

$$T = \frac{N!}{2 \cdot N} = \frac{(N-1)!}{2} \quad (1)$$

Approximate approaches are included of heuristic and meta-heuristic algorithms such as simulated annealing [11], tabu search [12], and swarm intelligence (SI) algorithms [13-25]. SI algorithms are population-based meta-heuristic algorithms, which have random-based global search strategies, and have attracted a great deal of attentions [26-32]. They able to carry out better search process toward other algorithms, and do not require the gradient information. These methods find a set of near-optimal solutions in a reasonable time rather than exact algorithms which can find the optimum solution but in exponential time. In recent years, the SI algorithms effectively have been developed for TSP, such as: genetic algorithm (GA) [13-17], particle swarm optimization (PSO) [18-20], ant colony optimization (ACO) [21-23] and artificial bee colony (ABC) [24-25].

In [13], a GA-based algorithm has been introduced for TSP. It uses a topological encoding scheme to form ordering of vertices in a directed graph. Also, Albayrak, *et. al* [17] have proposed a greedy sub tour mutation (GSTM) operator to improve the convergence of GA. It can efficiently search locally within the previous solutions like the other mutation operators.

The traditional PSO was proposed for the continuous problems. However some modifications of PSO have been applied for TSP. Wang, *et. al* [18] modified the PSO using the concepts of Adjustment Operator and Adjustment Sequence. In this algorithm, the particles not only adjust its own flying speed and the best individual of the swarm, but also learn from other individuals according to proposed certain probability. Additionally, the mutation of velocity was used. Shi, *et. al* [20] modified the subtraction operator between two particle positions in PSO. The crossover eliminated technique and two local search techniques were also executed their method. These local search techniques were used to accelerate the convergence speed, by employing the generalized chromosome.

Shang, *et. al* [21] combined ACO and association rule (AR) as a hybrid swarm intelligence based algorithm for the TSP. It is worth noting that the AR has been presented to find the best data sequence in data mining. Li, *et. al* [22] also presented an improved ACO, in which, a modified probability-based selection scheme is utilized by using Held-Karp lower bound in order to have a better trade-off between the influence of pheromone trail and heuristic information.

In [24] a novel ABC algorithm has been suggested to solve TSP so that it mixtures the route construction mechanism with path relining (PR). This method introduces attributes of the guiding solution into the initial solution to obtain high quality solutions as quickly as possible. The other ABC-based algorithm is a Hybrid Mutation-based ABC algorithm (named HMABC) to solve TSP [25], which employed the hybrid mutation scheme to search the neighbourhood of the found solutions, in order to achieve better solutions.

As mentioned above, many SI-based methods have been proposed for TSP. In this paper, we aim to carry out a comparison between SI algorithms, in order to evaluate the performance of SI algorithms for the routing problems like TSP. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In

section 2, the proposed framework of each EA for TSP has introduced. In section 3, experimental results are shown. And finally a comparison between SI algorithms for TSP is described in section 4.

2. SWARM INTELLIGENCE BASED SOLUTIONS FOR TSP

A routing solution in the TSP can be represented as a graph $G = (V, E)$, in which, $V = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is the set of all nodes (cities) within the problem graph, and $E = \{(i, j) | i, j \in V\}$ is the set of all possible edges between the nodes. More specifically, each node represents the position of a city, whereas each edge corresponds to a connection path between two cities. The distance d_{ij} which is associated with edge (i, j) , represents the Euclidean distance from city i to city j , and is calculated according to Eq. 2. The heuristic information is calculated before employing the SI algorithms at offline step. So, the distances of all edges were saved.

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

In all SI algorithms, iteratively after construction the solutions, the qualities of the gathered solutions are evaluated by the defined objective function, which is same for all SI algorithms. It can be evaluated for the each solution (a chromosome, a particle, an ant, or a bee) by simply calculating the sum of Euclidean distances of the consecutive edges within the tour as follows:

$$Cost_k = \sum_{l=1}^N d_l \quad (3)$$

To solve TSP by SI algorithms, at the first, an initial population is generated to search among N -dimension search space according to get an optimum tour. In order to generate the initial solutions, at first, a random city is selected as the initial node (e.g., city i). Then, the remained cities are consecutively added to the tour, until all cities will be selected. At the each step, the next city is chosen according to a defined probability which corresponds to the reverse of its distances from the current city. We called it the probability-based nearest neighbour (PNN) rule.

2.1. Proposed GA-based Algorithm for TSP

Genetic algorithm (GA) was invented firstly by Holland in 1975 [33]. In order to solve TSP via GA, each chromosome can be encoded by permutation coding to represent a tour. On the other hand, each gene within a chromosome is a positive integer which means the ID of a city that the salesman is passing from that.

At first, the initial population of GA is randomly constructed by the PNN rule, in such a way that no repetitive city occurs within each chromosome. At the every iteration, quality of each chromosome is evaluated according to the predefined objective function in Eq. 3. As a result, all solutions are sorted from the best to the worst, according to the objective function. Then, some of the best ones are selected as parents based on a selection strategy, e.g., roulette wheel selection or elitism selection. After performing the crossover operation, the mutation operator is applied for some gathered offspring, to change randomly in the value of some genes.

A. Crossover

In order to generate an offspring via crossover operator, two parents are randomly chosen among the best individuals. There is an essential problem in the crossover step for solving the TSP: with a traditional crossover operator, when two correct parents are recombined, each of the resultant offspring is malformed. Because after the crossover, some repetitive cities are appears in the offspring. Some methods were introduced aim to overcome this problem: Sheng *et al.* [15] used a greedy crossover operation (GX). Majumdar *et al.* [14] proposed modified cycle crossover (MCX), modified order crossover (MOX), and sequence crossover(SX) operators. Choi *et al.* [16] had applied a partially matched crossover (PMX). Also, Xing *et al.* [34] proposed the same-site-copy-first principle. In the permutation encoding, the PMX and MOX crossover operators have been efficiently used.

In the MOX operator, some genes of the first parent are printed in the offspring, in the same positions. The rest of genes are taken in the same sequence order as in the second parent. We utilize the MOX operator with three crossover points at random positions. For the first offspring, the genes are copied from the first parent till the initial crossover point, also from the second point till the third point. Then the genes of the second parent are scanned, and the numbers of the second parent which are not within the first offspring, will be appear in the first offspring with the same order that they are came in the second parent. Illustration of MOX operator can be seen in Fig. 1. Also, the PMX operator works as follows: two crossover points are chosen at random positions. The second parts of the parents are exchanged, and then, each number of first parent that does not appear in the second part, is written in the first offspring in the same position. The remained numbers are appeared in the first offspring with the same sequence order as in the second parent. The operation of the PMX mechanism can be seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Illustration of the MOX crossover operator with three points on random positions.

Figure 2. Illustration of the PMX crossover operator with two points on random positions.

B. Mutation

In TSP, there are various mutation operators like swap, inversion, route and shift-change (RSC) [13-17]. Also, we have introduced neighbour swap (NS), neighbour shift-change (NSC), and neighbour change (NC) in [25], as some mutation operators for TSP. In the NS, two neighbour genes are randomly selected and exchanged together. The NSC selects two neighbour genes at random location within the offspring. Then, it shifts all remained genes between them with the same sequence. The NS and the NSC operations can be illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 3. Illustration of the NS mutation operation.

Figure 4. Illustration of the NSC mutation operation.

Also, the NC operator works as follow:

- One city is randomly selected as the initial city of the tour (e.g., the city i).
- A city must be selected in the neighborhood of the city i , in such a way that each has less distance, has more chance to be selected. The probability of city j is proportional to the inverse of its distance from the current city.
- The position of the city i and the lately selected city are determined in the solution.
- The simple shift-change is performed for the two selected cities.

C. Overall Steps in Proposed GA

In this paper, the MOX crossover operator and the NC mutation operator were employed. The proposed GA-based algorithm for TSP can be described as follow:

Step 1: Initialization

- Set the parameters.
- Set the **max-iterations**.

Step 2: Generation of initial population by PNN rule.

- Each chromosome selects a random tour based on PNN rule and constructs a solution.

Step 3: Evaluation of the gathered solutions by Eq.3

Step 4: Check the stop criterion:

- Stop, if the maximum number of iterations reached. Otherwise, continue.

Step 5: Generation of new population. These 3 actions are done until completion the population:

- **Selection:** two best chromosomes are chosen as parents by Elitism strategy.
- **Crossover:** MOX operator is applied to generate two offspring from the parents.
- **Mutation:** the NC operator is done with a defined probability for some offspring.

Step 6: Go to step 3 and continue.

2.2. Proposed ACO-based Algorithm for TSP

Ant colony optimization (ACO) proposed by Dorigo [35] and firstly applied to solve TSP. ACO inspired by the swarm based behaviour of real ants to find the shortest paths. Ants deposit a chemical material (called pheromone), when they walking. In order to perform ACO for TSP, an idea should be used to mimic the behaviour of real ants with artificial ones walking around the problem graph, as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Graph representation in TSP: ant is firstly at node a_1 and should add a next city to its path. For example it chooses the city a_3, a_6, a_4, a_5, a_2 , respectively, based on transition probability rule. Finally, the ant comes back to the initial city a_1 and completes its tour.

A. Construction the suitable solutions

Given a colony of k artificial ants; these ants perform a number of iterations. At the every iteration, each ant starts from an initial city, randomly. Then, it consecutively selects the next cities according to the probability rule, until it completes the tour. The probability of i -th ant located at the city i to select the city j as its next city is calculated as follows [36]:

$$P_{ij}^k(t) = \frac{\tau_{ij}^\alpha(t) \cdot \eta_{ij}}{\sum_l \tau_{il}^\alpha(t) \cdot \eta_{il}}, \quad l, j \in G_k \quad (4)$$

where, G_k is the set of all conditional cities which have not been selected yet by the i -th ant, and τ_{ij} and η_{ij} are the pheromone amount and the heuristic information for choosing city j , respectively. Here, η_{ij} is calculated as $1/d_{ij}$, where d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between cities i and j . On the other hand, α is a parameter in the range of $[0,1]$ which define the relative importance between the pheromone trail and the heuristic information.

B. Pheromone updating

At the every iteration, all ant should be evaluated by means of the objective function. Then, two high-quality ants are chosen for the pheromone deposition on their edges: the first is the best ant in the current iteration, and the second is the global best ant found so far. The pheromone updating is done as follows:

$$\tau_{ij}^{t+1} = (1 - \lambda) \cdot \tau_{ij}^t + \begin{cases} D & \text{for edges of the best ant} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where τ_{ij}^t and τ_{ij}^{t+1} are the volume of pheromone on edge (i, j) respectively at iteration t and at the next iteration. Also, D is a constant parameter determining the pheromone deposition value, and λ is the amount of the evaporation factor.

C. Overall Steps in Proposed ACO

The main steps of proposed ACO-based algorithm can be summarized as follows:

Step 1: Initialization and set the parameters.

Step 2: Generation of initial solutions by PNN rule.

- Each ant selects a random tour based on PNN rule, and constructs a solution.

Step 3: Evaluation of achieved solution by ants, using Eq. 3.

Step 4: Check the stop criterion:

- Stop, if the maximum number of iterations reached. Otherwise, continue.

Step 5: Pheromone updating.

- **Evaporation:** It is done for the all edges of the graph.
- **Deposition:** It is performed only for the edges of the two best ants.

Step 6: Generation of new solutions according to Eq. 4.

Step 7: Go to step 3.

2.3. Proposed PSO-based Algorithm for TSP

Particle swarm optimization (PSO) introduced by Eberhart and Kennedy in 1995 [37], inspired by social behaviour of bird flocking and fish schooling. In the TSP, the position of each particle can be illustrated as $X_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iD})$, which defines a possible travelling path represented by the i -th particle with the city sequence of $x_{i1} \rightarrow x_{i2} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow x_{iD}$. The velocity of each particle is represented as $V_i = (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{iD})$. Here, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, where m is the number of all particles, and D is the number of all cities within the problem graph. The velocities of the particles which are far from an own optimum or the general optimum, can sharply rise, but the velocities of high-quality particles change slightly.

The PSO is initialized randomly by generation a population of solutions called particles. The qualities of the gathered particles are evaluated by the predefined objective function in Eq. 3. The movement of each particle at the every iteration is influenced by the own best experience (called '*pbest*'), and the global best solution found by all particles so far (called '*gbest*'). On the other hand, each particle is updated by influence of the both *pbest* and *gbest*. Positions and velocities of particles dynamically are updated according to following equations:

$$V_{id}(t + 1) = w_i \cdot V_{id}(t) + C_1 \cdot rand. (p_{best_{id}}(t) - x_{id}(t)) + C_2 \cdot rand. (g_{best_{gd}} - x_{id}(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$x_{id}(t + 1) = x_{id}(t) + v_{id}(t + 1) \quad (7)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are two constant parameters so called acceleration coefficients. Also, $rand$ is a random number uniformly distributed in the range of $[0,1]$. Moreover, w_i is the inertia weight, often decreasing linearly from W_{max} to W_{min} during execute algorithm that tunes as Eq. 8, where It_{max} is the maximum number of iteration, and It is the current iteration.

$$w_i = w_{max} + (It/It_{max}) \cdot (w_{max} - w_{min}) \quad (8)$$

In order to solve TSP via PSO, each particle should be represented as a string of positive integers. So the classical updating scheme for velocities and positions (Eqs. 6 and 7) cannot be used for the TSP, and a mechanism must be employed in order to iteratively update the positions toward the p_{best} and g_{best} .

In this work, we propose a hybrid crossover-based scheme to combine the current position of the particle with its p_{best} and the g_{best} . In this way at the first, the two strings which represent the position of p_{best} and g_{best} are combined together using the PMX crossover operation, and generate the *Velocity*. Then the current particle moves toward the *Velocity* using the MOX crossover operator. Finally, the new generated string is considered as the particle position for the next iteration. The overall steps of proposed PSO-based algorithm can be summarized as follows:

Step 1: Initialization and set the parameters.

Step 2: Generation of initial particles by PNN rule.

Step 3: Evaluation of the particles by Eq. 3.

Step 4: Determination of p_{best} of each particle, and g_{best} .

Step 5: Generation of the new population:

- The p_{best} of each particle is combined with the g_{best} using the PMX crossover operator, and the *Velocity* of that particle is made.
- Each particle moves toward the both p_{best} and g_{best} , by combination of the particle with its *Velocity* using the MOX crossover operator.

Step 6: Check the stop criterion:

- Stop, if the maximum number of iterations reached. Otherwise, continue.

Step 7: Go to step 3.

2.4. Proposed ABC-based Algorithm for TSP

Artificial bee colony (ABC) is proposed by Karaboga in 2006 [38] which inspired of the intelligent foraging behaviour of honey bees. In ABC, the colony consists of three groups of bees: employed bees, onlookers and scouts [39]. Each employed goes onto the previously visited food source area in her memory and achieves a new food source. Provided that the nectar (fitness) of the new solution be higher than the previous one, the employed bee forgets the previous solution and memorizes the new one. Otherwise, she keeps the previous. Each onlooker gives the

information of employed bees, and makes decision to select an employed through the shared information from the dances of the employed bees within the hive. Also, those employed bees which were abandoned, become scout, and start randomly search among the search space, as same as the initial solution generation.

In order to solve TSP via ABC, a food source represents a feasible tour. Also, the nectar of the food source corresponds to the quality of the tour. Initially, a set of food sources are randomly generated by employed bees. Then, the nectar (fitness) of the gathered food sources are determined by means of the objective function. As a result, the quality of the initial solutions is evaluated.

D. Selection of the best employed bees

After all employed bees have completed their search and constructed their solutions, they come back into the hive and share the information about the quality of the food sources with the onlookers waiting within the hive. The probability of k -th employed bee to be selected by an onlooker can be expressed as follows:

$$P_k = \frac{N_k^\alpha}{\sum_{i=1}^N N_i^\alpha} \quad (9)$$

where N_k is the amount of nectar within food source k , and $\sum_{i=1}^N N_k$ is the total amount of achieved nectar. N_k is considered as $1/Cost_k$. Increasing in the value of α ($\alpha > 1$) leads to select the better bees as scouts.

E. Recruitment process for onlooker bees

After selecting the best employed bees, the recruitment process should be performed, in such a way that some onlookers are assigned for the each best employed bee. The more quality the employed exists, the more onlookers would be assigned. The number of selected onlookers for the each of the best employed can be calculated as $S_i = \beta \times (P_i/H) + \gamma$, where S_i is the percentage of the onlookers selected for the i -th best employed bee. P_i is the preference number of the i -th employed, and H is the number of all selected best employed bees. Also, β and γ are two constants which determine the recruitment scheme. If $\beta=0$, the number of selected onlookers for the all best employed bees are determined uniformly. The larger β , the more onlookers are selected for the higher quality employed bee.

F. Neighbourhood search mechanism

In this step, each onlooker and its assigned employed bee go onto the neighbourhood area of the food source which has been found by the employed bee, in the previous iteration. In order to generate a new solution in the vicinity of the current one, some parts of the current tour should be changed. In order to do that, we proposed a hybrid mutation scheme in [25] for searching the neighbourhood of each scout bee. In this way, three mutation operators consist of NSC, NS and NC are used, which each of them has the own advantage and prevents the search process from a kind local minima. Each bee uses the NC operator with the %50 probability, and the chance of applying the NS and the NSC operators are %20 and %30 respectively.

G. Overall Steps in Proposed ABC

As mentioned above, the main steps of the ABC-based routing can be summarized as follows:

Step 1: Initialization and set the parameters of ABC.

Step 2: Generation of initial solutions by PNN rule.

- Each employed bee construct a solution according to PNN rule.

Step 3: Evaluation of the achieved solutions by Eq. 3.

Step 4: Updating of the global best solution found so far.

Step 5: Selection of the best employed bees by onlookers, and performing the recruitment process.

Step 6: Check the stop criterion:

- Stop, if the maximum number of iterations reached. Otherwise, continue.

Step 7: Neighbourhood search using the hybrid mutation-based local search scheme.

Step 8: Go to step 3 and continue.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS

3.1. Simulation Settings

All of the experiments tested on a PC with 2.53^{GHZ} processor and 4^{GB} memory running MATLAB R2012b in windows 8. The experiments were carried out on benchmark problems from TSPLIB [40] as seen in Table 1. The first column is the name of problems, the second is the number of cities within the problem, and the third is the best tour length. To adjust the operators and controllable parameters of the each SI algorithm, different operators and values were evaluated and the best ones were considered for the final simulations. The population size and the maximum number of iterations were set to the same value of 100 and 500, respectively, for the all SI algorithms.

Table 1. Benchmarks.

Problem	Number of Cities	Optimal Solution
At48	48	10628
Eil51	51	426
Berlin52	52	7542
Eil76	76	538
KroA100	100	21282
Lin105	105	14379
Beir127	127	118282
KroA200	200	29368

Tuning the GA: In order to perform GA, the PMX and MOX, NSC, NS and NC operators are evaluated as the crossover and mutation operators. With respect to the obtained results, the MOX crossover operator and the NC mutation operator were selected for applying GA in our experiments. Setting the parameters of GA can be summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Parameter setting for the proposed GA-based algorithm.

Parameter	Value
Max Iteration	500
Number of Chromosomes	100
Selection Type	Elitism Selection

Parameter	Value
Number of Selected Parents	5
Crossover Operator	MOX
Number of Points for Crossover	3 points
Max distance of two neighbours for applying mutation	Number of Cities/5
Mutation operator	NC
Mutation probability	0.5/ Number of Cities

Tuning the ACO: The pheromone of all edges is considered within the range of [0,1], where the initial pheromone was set to 0.5. Different values were evaluated for the evaporation factor λ and finally it was set to $\lambda=0.15$. The pheromone deposition on the edges of the two selected best ants was defined as $D=0.5$. The parameter setting for ACO can be shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameter setting for the proposed ACO-based algorithm.

Parameter	Value
Max Iteration	500
Number of Ants	100
Number of Candida ants	2
Initial Pheromone of All Edges	0.5
Evaporation factor (λ) (Eq. 5)	%15
Deposition amount (D) (Eq. 5)	0.5
α (Eq. 4)	2
Max Iteration	500

Tuning the PSO: For PSO, the three point MOX crossover was used on random positions, in order to combine the $pbest$ and $gbest$. And finally the three point MOX crossover was performed to combine the particle with the $pbest$ and $gbest$, aim to move the particle toward them.

Table 4. Parameter setting for the proposed PSO-based algorithm.

Parameter	Value
Max Iteration	500
Number of Particles	100
Type of Combination of $pbest$ and $gbest$ to Generate the <i>Velocity</i>	PMX Operator
Type of Combination the Particle with its <i>Velocity</i>	MOX Operator

Tuning the ABC: As mentioned above, a hybrid mutation scheme was used, in order to search the neighbourhood of the solutions found by the scouts. We tested some combination of mutation operators in our previous work [31]. Respect to the obtained results, we employed the NS, NSC, and NC operators with their corresponding probability.

Table 5. Parameter setting for the proposed ABC-based algorithm.

Parameter	Value
Max Iteration	500
Number of Employed Bees	100
Number of Scout Bees	5
Max distance of two neighbours for applying mutation	Number of Cities/5
Probability of applying NS operator	%20
Probability of applying NSC operator	%30
Probability of applying NC operator	%50

Parameter	Value
β	-20
γ	32
H	5
α	2

3.2. Simulation Results

We performed each EA 10 times. The best achieved solution, and the average for 10 runs, using each algorithm can be shown in Table 6. The first column is the problem names; the second, third, fourth and fifth columns are consist of the best found tour length, and the average for 10 runs, respectively using GA, ACO, PSO, and ABC. Moreover, comparison of the running time of the different algorithms can be seen in Table 7. The best solution achieved by ABC for some problems is shown in Figures 6 to 9. In these Figures, the x-axis and y-axis describe the location of cities. Each point is corresponding with each city.

Table 6. Comparison of the average and best error rate for 10 runs (in percentage).

Problem	GA		ACO		PSO		ABC	
	Best	Avg.	Best	Avg.	Best	Avg.	Best	Avg.
At48	1.23	2.16	0.72	1.64	0.67	0.92	0.31	0.82
Eil51	1.71	3.52	0.43	2.88	0.2	1.37	0	0.77
Berlin52	1.62	2.41	0	2.22	1.03	1.91	0.27	0.91
Eil76	2.03	4.64	0	2.93	0	1.15	0	1.15
KroA100	1.92	3.29	1.25	3.78	1.37	2.56	1.08	1.67
Lin105	2.67	4.17	1.08	3.92	0.93	2.57	0.36	1.72
Beir127	3.04	4.45	2.12	4.89	1.25	3.41	1.25	2.12
KroA200	4.33	6.45	2.45	5.78	1.87	3.61	1.37	2.08

Table 7. Comparison of the running time (in seconds).

Problem	GA	ACO	PSO	ABC
At48	35	53	45	31
Eil51	38	61	49	35
Berlin52	38	65	53	32
Eil76	42	102	84	29
KroA100	52	155	119	36
Lin105	57	168	123	44
Beir127	68	213	175	45
KroA200	107	366	288	94

Figure 6. The Best Solution for Berlin52, Found by ABC.

Figure 7. The Best Solution for At48, Found by ABC.

Figure 8. The Best Solution for Lin105, Found by ABC.

Figure 9. The Best Solution for KroA100, Found by ABC.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we compared the performance of the four famous SI algorithms include of GA, PSO, ACO, and ABC to solve TSP. Respect to the obtained results, ABC achieved better performance compared with the other SI algorithms, especially for high dimension problems. ACO has memory, in which, the ants that were optimal in the past, are tugged to return towards due to their deposited pheromone. However, as the number of cities be increased, the performance of ACO is reduced, because of complexity in running time. So, it is recommended for the problems with fewer than 80 cities. Although GA and PSO have very good performance for the class of parameter optimization problems, but they have some limitations for the permutation problems such TSP: the traditional scheme of GA and PSO lead to generate some repetitive cities in their solutions. Although some modifications have been utilized to handle this problem, these algorithms cannot compete with ACO and ABC. The ABC algorithm has a strong global search capability in the problem space and can efficiently find optimal tour. For some of the high dimensional problems, the other SI algorithms often trapped in local minima points after finding a sub-optimal solution. However, ABC can efficiently explore in the search space until an optimal solution found. The ABC algorithm considers both running time and solution quality. ABC is quicker in finding optimal solution than the other SI algorithms; also it is quite simple and easy to apply. The performances of other SI algorithms are reduced especially for high dimension problems, and ABC can be employed to guarantee achieving the optimal solution.

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